

DYNAMIC AND TERRITORIAL FEATURES OF TOLERANCE AMONG FUTURE OFFICERS

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Abstract. *In World educational and scientific centers, the development of professionally significant quality of future offices, the impact of educational-military situations on the psychological formation of Cadets, the dynamics of the manifestation of tolerance in offices, the differentiation of individual-psychological, social qualities affecting the development of tolerance in future offices are being studied. In this regard, we tried to highlight in this article the issues aimed at the formation of tolerance in future offices through psychological characteristics, specific aspects of tolerance in the system of personality values, national genius in cadets, characteristics of ethnic identity.*

Keywords: *tolerance, ethnic identity, national genius, ethnicity, social qualities*

INTRODUCTION. Ideological wars taking place in the world, interaction in a multinational society, conflicts between different beliefs are raising the issue of socio-psychological research of the problem of tolerance in an individual. In particular, the tactical actions of military officers are of great importance in this process, and the phenomena occurring at ideological outposts indicate the importance of constructive resolution of conflicts in their interpersonal relationships, the development of “colorful culture of the world, specific styles in the manifestation of personality and respect, acceptance and correct understanding of human individuality” [1]. In this regard, the issues of increasing psychological training

in accordance with the directions of professional activity of future office workers, the formation of socio - national genius, the development of a sense of national and ethnic identity, the qualities of social tolerance remain relevant.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODS. N. K. Roerich, the upbringing of patience is the main condition for piety, self-rejection and self-rejection, he raised Uzi and uzga in love and recognition. N. K. Roerich expressed the opinion that bagrikenglik influenced him by the form of his adjective as he advanced: "every person I meet needs me to feel pain and sadness. Shun is designed so that a person can have strong tolerant human qualities, respect him and achieve consensus".[2] Famous researcher of communication psychology L.I. It is possible to agree with rymshina's opinion in the study of tolerance as an ideal position. “The problem in the approach to the system of values is that the person manifests as masters, values and content, it is they who, on the one hand, determine the inner world of the individual, and on the other - the one that determines the true hulk of the individual, is motivational - controlling” [3] such an approach has a future, since tolerance allows.

Researcher V.M. Zolotukhin, in his work “two concepts of tolerance”, is able to analyze the essence of the concept of “tolerance” while calculating with the multidimensionality of social life and, recognizing it, determine the psychological content of tolerance. In his opinion, tolerance is a practical tool that, on the one hand, governs human activities, forms a special type of worldview, and on the other - allows effective resolution of conflicts and conflicts.

V.M.Zolotukhina's research work "tolerance as a problem of philosophical Anthropology" reveals the anthropological basis of tolerance, in which tolerance is characterized as a way of human existence. [4]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The manifestation of tolerance in a person, including in offices, largely depends on professional conditions, the environment and, most importantly, on the system of personality values. It is important to research the influence of their value system on the manifestation of tolerance qualities, as we know that office workers come into contact with different layers of population during their professional career.

The system of personality values refers to a stable part of his interests, views, motivational sphere, the "volitional component" of the human way of life. While the system of personality values performs the tasks of targeting, evaluating, motivating, self-control and managing in a person's life, a series with a specific arrangement is maturing, maturing, fluffy, mature, perfect, perfect, perfect, enlightened. Perfection also means the maturity of the mental, spiritual, moral, the mastery of the profession of his choice, the ability to form as a person and build and create with noble ideas and intentions.

An interesting case is that the quality of perfection has given the opposite correlation of the value system with aspects that indicate the perception of life, the attitude towards justice, the attitude of a person towards himself and those around him. And the controllability of life means that a person understands, understands and harmonizes with his way of life. We can explain the reverse connection between these two phenomena by the fact that the extreme cases in the lifestyles of office workers live in a "barracks" structure, far from the family's bosom. Emergencies in the life of future office workers cause a little "chaos" in personal life. As a result, the desire for professional comicity in future office workers leads to the fact that life management is spent in a little more rakurs. The next criterion is the inverse relationship between self-control and perfection. Self-control depends on the individual's self-attitude. In this case, too, a slightly incomprehensible situation was observed. Because perfection had to be in harmony with self-control. This condition, observed in our eyes, is also associated with the professional formation of future office workers. Future office workers learn to control and control themselves in the process of professional formation. However, the conditions in the professional training facility of office workers, a kind of strict discipline, have led to negative associations between the two phenomena. There is one aspect that should be paid attention to in future offices to manage the phenomena that are happening around them, even if the desired action attempts to develop strategies emergency situations related to "service activities" sometimes limit lifestyle management. Therefore, negative associations have been identified between the two phenomena.

The next indicator is defined by the fact that the sense of ethnicity has positive associations with the criterion of the righteousness of life ($r=0.28$; $p\leq 0.01$). This state of affairs means that the perception, feeling of one's own origin, national affiliation of future office workers is in harmony with an understanding of the Justice of life, the magnetism of what is happening. The high level of confidence of future office workers in the Justice of life is observed in harmony with his ethnicity, the strength of his national identity. The harmony of the sense of ethnicity in future offices with the righteousness of life leads, first of all, to the perception of the ethnic group in the prism of its own Justice, strengthening the social status of the individual, an authentic assessment of the professional and peer community, the emergence of a differential approach in interpersonal relationships in a unique way. As a result, the identity formation of tolerance to ethnic identity is observed in future offices. Another important aspect of

our research lies in the fact that the use of one language or another in future offices has a positive connection with the righteousness of life ($r=0.21$; $p\leq 0.05$). The future Officer will be forced to establish a dialog with representatives of different nationalities from the point of view of his professional activities. As a result, the assimilation of various languages, their use in activities leads to the formation of a tolerant attitude towards the culture of representatives of the opposing nationalities in this language. This situation, on the other hand, shows the worldview of future office workers, the level of intellectualism, the way of life of peoples, relationships in the social layer, fairness in the system of society, bringing their culture to a deeper development. By using the languages of people of different nationalities, the system of concepts about the righteousness of life becomes more stable. Therefore, positive associations have been identified between these two phenomena.

A specific interesting case in our empirical result has been observed in the relationship between social tolerance and values. In this, too, social tolerance did not have significant links with the system of personality values in the 1st stage cadets. The main reason for this is when in the cadets of the 1st stage there is a situation of adaptation to extreme situations associated with the educational process. Because, according to the dynamics of the formation of a group of cadets assembled for one purpose from different regions, in this period it is the period when people are adapting to each other, to the environment, studying each other. Therefore, the degree of interaction of cadets with their groups is more aimed at affirming their individuality, and the level of social tolerance will not have led to insufficient activation of certain individual psychological characteristics in the system of personality values. However, in Phase 4 courses, social tolerance is defined as the positivity of the World ($r=-0.41$; $p\leq 0.10$), the controllability of life ($r=-0.42$; $p\leq 0.05$). In fact, social tolerance occurs when an individual harmonizes with a group, when "I" accepts "us", when the perception of people in the prism of social values, Masters, stereotypes is activated, and symbolizes the socio-psychological maturity of a person. The peculiarity of our results is that social tolerance has given an inverse correlation with certain aspects in the value system. In particular, the fact that in Stage 4 cadets social tolerance has an inverse correlation with the positivity of the world means that they are able to adequately perceive phenomena occurring in the environment, conflicts between nations or, conversely, interaction on the basis of critical thinking, not exaggerating the positive side of Group vocations, but also unleashing constructive criticism. This also means that they analyze the Vagrancy occurring within ethnic groups with extreme rigor from a professional point of view and show a low level of resilience, tolerance in Group Relations another important aspect of our dissertation research has a positive connection with the Justice of life ($r=0.21$; $p\leq 0.05$) of the use of this or that language in bo'lganligidir. The future Officer will be forced to establish a dialog with representatives of different nationalities from the point of view of his professional activities. As a result, the assimilation of various languages, their use in activities leads to the formation of a tolerant attitude towards the culture of representatives of the opposing nationalities in this language. This situation, on the other hand, shows the worldview of future office workers, the level of intellectualism, the way of life of peoples, relationships in the social layer, fairness in the system of society, bringing their culture to a deeper development. By using the languages of people of different nationalities, the system of concepts about the righteousness of life becomes more stable. Therefore, positive associations have been identified between these two phenomena.

Conclusion. Based on the above data, it is established that there is a correlation between tolerance and base beliefs in prospective offices.

We would like to say that the feeling of national immunity has an important place in the offices, because this crisis means their harmony with the nation, the fate of the Motherland, the people, living with their fate, the responsibility to elat. Therefore, the inflexibility of the fate of the nation and the land in future offices, its progress, leads to the fact that people are perceived in a good, optimistic, kind and most basic humanistic way.

The National immunity of future offices will cause representatives of the nationality to be perceived as better than everyone else. The righteousness of life in future offices, whose national immunity is strongly developed, is characterized by the fact that progress in the land is built on its own criterion of Justice, harmonizes with a sense of pride. Therefore, positive associations have been identified among these phenomena.

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